

**EMPOWERMENT AMONG STUDENTS:A DISCIPLINE BASED
COMPARATIVE STUDY**

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Abstract

Present study was aimed to explore the level of empowerment among engineering, management and education discipline students and to explore the difference in empowerment of engineering, management and education discipline students. It was hypothesized that there is no significant difference in empowerment of engineering, management and education discipline students. The findings of the study revealed that 08 percent students of education discipline have low level empowerment, 63 percent have average level empowerment and 29 percent students of education discipline have high level empowerment. While 30 percent students of engineering discipline have low level empowerment, 46 percent students have average level empowerment and 24 percent students of engineering discipline have high level empowerment. On the other hand 33 percent students of management discipline have low level empowerment, 44 percent students have average level empowerment and 23 percent students of management discipline have high level empowerment. The results explored that empowerment of engineering, management and education discipline students significantly vary from each other's discipline. The difference in empowerment of engineering, management and education discipline students was further analyzed using t-test and all the values have been found to be significant at 0.01 level of significance.

Empowerment concept is explained and defined by various disciplines i.e. social work, psychology, education, community psychology. In addition, empowerment concept is largely used in different phenomenon, such as: student empowerment, women empowerment, teacher empowerment etc. Ashcroft (1987) described empowerment as personal power, which can exist in both personal and social spheres. Ashcroft believed that empowerment should be a philosophy of education. Empowering is not something that can be turned on and off but needs to be consistent and persuasive. Kreisberg (1992) defined empowerment as gaining control over one's own life and decisions that affect him. He suggested that empowerment is enabled by improving lives of a community and community members through dialogue and working collaboratively. Individuals can be empowered to take control over their lives and resources through the development of social skills.

At present time the term student empowerment has become an important point of discussion. It sits alongside such ideas as student participation and student engagement. Behind all of these ideas of student empowerment and participation are similar assumptions and approaches to young people. These emphasize young people as assets, rather than as potential societal problems. Therefore a student empowerment approach concentrates on building the personal strength in young people, rather than focusing on their deficits, whether real or assumed. Panitz and Panitz (2004) the empowerment of students produces an environment which fosters maturity and responsibility in their learning. The teacher becomes a facilitator instead of a director and the student becomes a willing participant instead of a passive follower. Smith, Trautman, & Schelvan (2004) there are many strategies a teacher can employ to foster student empowerment and inclusion like: Educate students about deficiencies, provide social skills, teach friendship skills, provide ample praise who are working together, structure class activities to encourage peer collaboration, teach and address stereotype, actively include the student in all classroom activities, create a classroom friendly environment for everyone. Karten (2005); Salend (2001) including students with disabilities into the regular education classroom requires

deliberate strategies that move beyond a student's physical presence in the classroom. Actual classroom attendance is not inclusion. Students with disabilities who are included with their typically developing peers should be engaged in the same classroom lessons as their peers, i.e. social inclusion is encouraged. Pearrow and Pollak (2009) examined the effect of empowerment of youth in urban settings for addressing social injustice. Houser and Frvmier (2009) investigated the effectiveness of empowered learners to perform classroom tasks and explored that students feel more competent in the classroom, find the required tasks more meaningful, and feel they have an impact on their learning process.

Youth empowerment approaches concentrate on building personal strength in young people. So we understand empowerment as process through which young people are able to increase their participation in private and public decisions. Empowerment is the development of knowledge, skills and abilities in learner to enable them to control and develop their own learning. The teacher can also help the student by telling them the value of student empowerment and will be benefitted from findings of this study. Very fewer studies were found to be on this topic till now, so to fill this gap the investigator has chosen this study.

OBJECTIVES

1. To study the level of empowerment among engineering, management and education discipline students.
2. To study the difference in empowerment of engineering, management and education discipline students.

HYPOTHESIS

1. There is no significance difference in the level of empowerment among engineering, management and education discipline students.
2. There is no significance difference in empowerment of engineering, management and education discipline students.

METHOD OF RESEARCH

All the students of engineering, management and education disciplines of Lovely Professional University, Punjab constituted the population for the study. 600 students from engineering, management and education disciplines were selected for the study. To make the data representative to the different disciplines stratified random sampling technique was used. The information about student empowerment was collected through student Empowerment Scale by *Kumar, A. and Anita (2012)* and general information about the subjects like name; address, gender and discipline were collected through information sheet. To test the significance of the variables under study, statistical techniques i.e. Mean, SD, Q1 and Q3, and t-test and percentage were be applied.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The present study aimed at studying empowerment among students of engineering, management and education disciplines. To conduct this study investigator required information regarding empowerment scores, gender and the disciplines of the students (engineering, management, education). Information regarding empowerment of students was collected through empowerment scale by Kumar and Chahal (2012) while information regarding gender and their discipline was collected through information sheet. After collecting the required information for present study and applying appropriate statistical techniques, the results have been presented under the following heads.

1. Level of empowerment among engineering, management and education discipline students

The first objective of the present study was to know the empowerment among engineering, management and education discipline students. The scores of empowerment scale of the engineering,

management and education discipline students were calculated and the mean value and S.D. of the empowerment scores has been found to be 181 and 25 respectively. On the basis of Q_1 and Q_3 values, three groups of empowerment scores were formed i.e. low level of empowerment group (LLE) those who scores less than 159, average level of empowerment group (ALE) having scores between 159-203 and high level of empowerment group (HLE) with scores higher than 203. The results have been presented in the table 1:

The table-1 revealed that 08 percent students of education discipline has low level empowerment, 63 percent has average level empowerment and 29 percent students of education discipline has high level empowerment. Similarly 30 percent students of engineering discipline has low level empowerment, 46 percent students average level empowerment and 24 percent students of engineering discipline has high level empowerment. While the results revealed that 33 percent students of management discipline has low level empowerment, 44 percent students has average level empowerment and 23 percent students of management discipline has high level empowerment.

The first hypothesis of the study stated that there is no significance difference in level of empowerment of engineering, management and education discipline students. The results of the study have not supported the said hypothesis. Thus hypothesis stands rejected. To the best knowledge of the investigator, no such study has been conducted to study the level of empowerment of engineering, management and education discipline students.

It may be concluded from the above discussion that student of education discipline were more empowered than students from engineering and management discipline. While the students from engineering and management discipline were more or less equally empowered. The investigator feel that reason behind this may be due to fact that students from education discipline are grown up individual because they get entry in their programme after graduation while students in engineering and management discipline get entry after senior secondary school.

2. Difference in empowerment of engineering, management and education discipline students

The second objective of the present study was to know the difference in empowerment of engineering, management and education discipline students. The empowerment scores of the engineering, management and education discipline students were calculated, mean and SD of different groups has been calculated and presented in tabular form in table-2. Thereafter empowerment scores of different groups i.e. engineering, management and education discipline students were compared using ANOVA and the results have been presented in the table-3:

The table-3 revealed that values of sum of squares and mean squares between groups have been found to be 13966.63 and 6983.32 respectively and the values of sum of squares and mean squares within groups have been found to be 366112.70 and 613.25 respectively. The F-value being 11.39 has been found to be significant at 0.01 level of significance. One of the objectives of the present study was to know the difference in empowerment of engineering, management and education discipline students. The results explored that empowerment of engineering, management and education discipline students significantly vary from each other's discipline.

The second hypothesis of the study stated that there is no significance difference in empowerment of engineering, management and education discipline students. The results of the study have not supported the said hypothesis. Thus hypothesis stands rejected. To the best knowledge of the investigator, no such study has been conducted to find difference in empowerment of engineering, management and education discipline students.

To further analyze the difference in empowerment of engineering, management and education discipline students t-test was applied and results has been presented in the table-4.

The table-4 revealed that the t-value between education and engineering students has been found to be 20.27, t-value between education and management students has been found to be 37.42, while t-value between engineering and management students has been found to be 17.91. All the values have been found to be significant at 0.01 level of significance.

It may be concluded from the above discussion that student from different discipline have significant difference in their empowerment. This may be due to fact that these disciplines have different circumstances and from students' parts leading to variation in their empowerment.

CONCLUSIONS

1. 08 percent students of education discipline have low level empowerment, 63 percent has average level empowerment and 29 percent students of education discipline have high level empowerment.
2. 30 percent students of engineering discipline have low level empowerment, 46 percent students have average level empowerment and 24 percent students of engineering discipline have high level empowerment.
3. 33 percent students of management discipline have low level empowerment, 44 percent students have average level empowerment and 23 percent students of management discipline have high level empowerment.
4. The results explored that empowerment of engineering, management and education discipline students significantly vary from each other's discipline.
5. To further analyze the difference in empowerment of engineering, management and education discipline students t-test was applied and all the values have been found to be significant at 0.01 level of significance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. There is a need to give more emphases for empowerment of engineering and management discipline students.
2. Leaders from the society, parents and teachers have to play key role in empowerment of our young generation.

SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

1. Student's empowerment can be studied with some other variables like emotional, cultural and psycho-social aspects of students.
2. Student's empowerment can be studied with some other demographic variables.

Table 1

EMPOWERMENT AMONG ENGINEERING, MANAGEMENT AND EDUCATION DISCIPLINE STUDENTS

Level	EDU	ENG	MGT	Range
LLE	8%	30%	33%	< 159
ALE	63%	46%	44%	159-203
HLE	29%	24%	23%	>203

Table 2

MEAN AND SD VALUES OF EMPOWERMENT SCORES OF ENGINEERING, MANAGEMENT AND EDUCATION DISCIPLINE STUDENTS

	EDU	ENG	MGT
N	150	204	246
Mean	189	180	177
SD	22.34	26.5	24.67

Table 3
SUMMARY OF ANOVA OF EMPOWERMENT OF ENGINEERING, MANAGEMENT AND EDUCATION DISCIPLINE STUDENTS

Groups	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Squares	F-Value
Between Groups	13966.63	2	6983.32	11.39
Within Groups	366112.70	597	613.25	P> .01 (4.65)
Total	380079.33	599		

Table 4
DIFFERENCE IN EMPOWERMENT OF ENGINEERING, MANAGEMENT AND EDUCATION DISCIPLINE STUDENTS

S. No.	Comparison of Groups	Mean Difference	Standard Error of Difference	t- Value
1	EDU & ENG	54	2.66	20.27
2	EDU & MGT	96	2.57	37.42
3	ENG & MGT	42	2.34	17.91

Figure 1
EMPOWERMENT AMONG ENGINEERING, MANAGEMENT AND EDUCATION DISCIPLINE STUDENTS

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